

EQUIPPING JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH LIFELONG LEARNING SKILLS IN TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Technology and Livelihood Education as one of the areas being studied under the basic education curriculum, is geared toward the development of technological proficiency, anchored on knowledge and information, entrepreneurial concepts, process and delivery, work values and life skills. This signifies that student should acquire proper mastery of knowledge, information, skills, and procedures, as well as appropriate work values and lifelong-learning skills. This study assessed the extent of manifestations of lifelong learning skills and level of competencies of Junior High School students in the Province of Batangas with the end goal of proposing a management plan for teachers. This study used the descriptive method of research to explain the variables under investigation and used a researcher-made questionnaire as the main instrument to identify the students' level of competencies. The respondents of the study included 135 school heads and 285 Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the Province of Batangas. Finding shows that lifelong-learning skills of students in beauty care, cookery and Information and Communication Technology in terms of critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, computer literacy and career and learning self-reliance are all moderately manifested by the students. Students are moderately knowledgeable and moderately competent in beauty care, cookery and Information and Communication Technology. Student development in terms of work attitude is moderately manifested while in terms of work skills, they are moderately competent. The top three issues and challenges relative to meeting TESDA standards are strengthening the technical skills and managerial skills of TLE teachers, integrating the curricula with 21st century skills to promote lifelong-learning and interest and capability to be National Certified in TLE areas. A management plan for teachers was proposed to strengthen students' competencies.

Keywords: TLE, life-long learning skills, competencies, Philippines